

Edible geophytes like blue dicks are phenomenally abundant on California's Channel Islands, as evidenced by the springtime bloom on Santa Cruz Island's West End. Blue dicks occur in various plant communities, but are especially prevalent in grassland/forb field communities, occurring throughout western North America and on all the islands off the California coast. Photograph by Eamon O'Byrne, TNC, Santa Cruz Island, spring 2014.

10,000 YEARS OF GEOPHYTE USE AMONG THE ISLAND CHUMASH OF THE NORTHERN CHANNEL ISLANDS

by Kristina M. Gill

Just off the southern California coast, the archipelago of the Santa Barbara Channel is comprised of four east-west trending islands, located between approximately 19 and 42 kilometers from the mainland today. When people first arrived during the last Ice Age, the islands of Anacapa (*Anyapakh* in

Chumash), Santa Cruz (*Limuw*), Santa Rosa (*Wi'ma*), and San Miguel (*Tuqan*) were connected as a single landmass commonly referred to by geologists and archaeologists as Santarosae (~10-12 km from the mainland). The Island Chumash and their ancestors thrived on these islands, adapting to sea level rise,

climate change, and population growth for at least 13,000 years, until Europeans drastically impacted their traditional way of life through disease, enslavement, and forced assimilation.

The Island Chumash are famous for their seafaring capabilities and strong maritime orientation, with a

long history of fishing, sea mammal hunting, and shellfishing. Plant foods were also important, supplying Islanders with carbohydrates needed to balance rich fats and proteins obtained from marine resources. Island archaeobotanical assemblages (the preserved remains of plants in archaeological sites) indicate that easily procurable plant foods high in carbohydrates were consistently the most important. These archaeobotanical remains are well preserved through carbonization and identifiable thousands of years after they were initially burned (often during cooking accidents) and deposited in habitation sites. Geophytes, small seeds (especially grasses and chenopods), and non-toxic pits like manzanita berries are frequently found in island sites, whereas toxic nuts such as acorns and cherry pits (*islay*) that require

extensive processing are much less common. Other plant foods were also used, but geophytes and small seeds appear to have been staple plant foods in Islander diets (Gill 2015; Gill and Hoppa 2016).

Geophytes are notably rich in carbohydrates and phenomenally abundant on the islands today, especially those in the *Brodiaea* complex (Themidaceae) (e.g., *Bloomeria* spp., *Brodiaea* spp., *Dichelostemma* spp., *Triteleia* spp.). The archaeobotanical corms could be any one of these four genera within the *Brodiaea* complex, but are morphologically indistinguishable when carbonized. Here, I refer to all ancient corms as blue dicks (*Dichelostemma capitatum*), which are the most likely candidate used extensively by the Island Chumash based on modern distributions and ethnographic information (Gill 2015). Blue dicks

are the most abundant geophyte on the islands today, especially in grasslands/forb fields, growing from sea level to the highest points, including Diablo Peak on Santa Cruz at 2,429 feet elevation.

Blue dicks reproduce both sexually (seed) and asexually (cormlets), with each mature corm capable of producing more than 15 cormlets annually that in turn produce their own cormlets the following year. Moreover, blue dicks corms on the islands are significantly larger than their mainland counterparts, measuring upwards of nearly 50 mm in diameter. Two possible explanations for the larger corms on the islands include a long history of Island Chumash harvest/selection for larger corms, and/or the lack of native burrowing or grazing herbivores present on the islands (e.g., gophers, deer, rabbits). Geophytes are espe-

Blue dicks field on southwest Santa Cruz Island near Pozo Canyon. Photograph by Kristina Gill, Santa Cruz Island, March 2014.

Hundreds of whole and nearly whole carbonized blue dicks corms were found associated with an earth oven at the Diablo Valdez site on Santa Cruz Island during excavation. Later detailed archaeobotanical analysis of soil samples revealed that blue dicks corms were used for nearly 6,000 years of occupation at this site, from ~5,800 years ago until around AD 1800. Blue dicks corms are the most frequently identified food plant on the northern islands, found in nearly all sites where archaeobotanical analysis has been done. K. Gill is pictured. Photograph by Terry Joslin, Santa Cruz Island, August 2011.

cially fecund on the islands today and the Island Chumash would have had no competition (aside from other Islanders) for this incredible food resource (Gill 2015).

Ethnographic use of edible geophytes, and blue dicks in particular, is extensively documented throughout much of California as well as in the Santa Barbara Channel region.

Modern blue dicks corms and underground storage organs of other geophytes on the Channel Islands are significantly larger than their mainland counterparts, measuring upwards of nearly 50 mm in diameter. The larger island corms may be the result of millennia of selection by Island Chumash and/or a lack of native burrowing and browsing herbivores (e.g., gophers, squirrels, deer, rabbits) that are common in mainland California, and that target blue dicks corms, shoots, and flowers as a food source. Photograph by Kristina Gill, Santa Cruz Island, July 2014.

Among the Chumash, the name *cacomite* (derived from the Nahuatl word *cacomitil* and introduced by the Spanish) was most commonly applied to blue dicks, as was the Chumash name *shiq'o'n* (Gill 2015; Timbrook 2007). *Shiq'o'n* was harvested using a digging stick, often weighted with a perforated stone (a.k.a “donut stone”). Fernando *Kitsepawit* Librado, an important Chumash consultant who worked with ethnographer John P. Harrington in the early 1900s, indicated that *shiq'o'n* was particularly important on the islands with several families involved in harvesting and cook-

Digging stick weights, also known as “donut stones,” are one of the most prevalent artifacts found on the Channel Islands, and have been identified in dateable contexts to at least the last 7,500 years. Donut stones have a single hole drilled through the middle and vary in size, shape, and extent of modification around the edges. These artifacts were typically affixed towards the base of digging sticks and used to provide more weight and leverage. The proportion of digging stick weights found on the islands (87%) compared with the adjacent mainland (13%) is quite high (Sutton 2014), further indicating that geophyte procurement was especially important on the islands. Photograph is by Kristina Gill, San Miguel Island, August 2012.

ing large quantities in earth ovens measuring over a meter across (Timbrook 2007).

Archaeobotanical data confirm ethnographic records that blue dicks corms were the most important Island Chumash plant food, with evidence of their use for nearly 10,000 years. Island sites generally have re-

markably well preserved stratigraphy (due to a lack of burrowing animals) that allows for plant remains within a given stratum to be radiocarbon dated directly and/or associated with a specific occupation layer. Aggregated extant archaeobotanical data from 26 sites on Santa Cruz and San Miguel Islands comparing densities and frequencies of carbonized blue dicks corms and corm fragments through time show no statistically significant change in their use over this 10,000-year span (Gill and Hoppa 2016). A similar pattern was also identified at a single site (Diablo Valdez) on Santa Cruz Island, where I documented no significant change in the use of blue dicks for nearly 6,000 years, using measures of density, frequency, and ratios to total plant weight (Gill 2015). A well-preserved earth oven associated with hundreds of carbonized blue dicks

corms was found during excavations at Diablo Valdez, confirming its primary function as a *shiq'o'n* cooking feature, the first of its kind to be identified archaeologically on the islands. While other plant remains from the Diablo Valdez site also show a similar pattern of consistent use through time, blue dicks corms were the most abundant and most frequently identified plant food.

Although most ethnographic literature in California indicate blue dicks corms were harvested in the spring after flowering, a second season of harvest has been documented on the islands during the fall. Blue dicks corms undergo seasonal morphological changes on an annual basis that can be identified on carbonized archaeobotanical speci-

Fernando Kitsepawit Librado, Chumash, demonstrates the use of a digging stick with no weight attached, near Ventura, CA, around 1912. Photograph courtesy of the Braun Research Library Collection, Autry Museum, Los Angeles; Plate 708.

mens (Gill 2014). The mature parent corms exhibit smooth sides in the late spring/summer, with adventitious root growth occurring around the base of the corm in the fall, as the corm emerges from summer dormancy in anticipation of fall and winter rains. The corm then appears to “divide” in the winter, where the old corm withers from its base, using its reserved starches to develop a new corm on top in preparation for flowering, again exhibiting smooth sides that remain through spring flowering and summer dormancy (Gill 2014). Cormlets (clones of the parent corm) follow a different morphological trajectory in their first year, and are sometimes found archaeologically as well, although much less frequently than mature

corms. Both the spring/summer (smooth) and fall (adventitious root growth) stages of seasonal morphological changes in the corms have been documented on archaeobotanical specimens from 6,000 years of occupation at Diablo Valdez (Gill 2014, 2015) and from a site on Santa Rosa Island (SRI-666) that dates to approximately 8,500 years ago. These specimens dating to multiple time periods indicate a long tradition of employing at least two seasons of harvest for blue dicks on the islands.

The remarkably long history of Island Chumash geophyte use employing two seasons of harvest, with no significant change seen over nearly 10,000 years attests to the importance of blue dicks as a food staple and overall geophyte-based subsistence regime. Furthermore, it appears that the Islanders were actively engaged in managing their

wild blue dicks fields, including “tilling” the soil during the repeated process of harvesting *shiq'o'n*, replanting cormlets and primarily harvesting mature corms, and possibly using other means such as seed dispersal during fall harvest and fire. These types of landscape management strategies would have promoted growth and increased the habitat of blue dicks and other important economic grassland taxa throughout prehistory. Current land management regimes (i.e., fire suppression, lack of new disturbance/regular “tillage”) are vastly different from those that the islands experienced over the previous 13,000 years, and it remains to be seen how well island geophytes will fare in the future.

TOP: Excavations at two loci of Diablo Valdez, an upland village site on the northern side of Santa Cruz Island, revealed deep and well-stratified deposits spanning nearly 6,000 years of occupation. Various features including two earth ovens, a house floor, and hearth cleaning pits, indicate that this was primarily a domestic site where daily activities such as cooking took place in and around living areas. K. Gill is pictured. Photograph by Amber Marie Madrid, Santa Cruz Island, August 2011. • BOTTOM: Earth ovens were used for cooking large quantities of geophytes at a time, and were most often built and used communally. Chumash consultant Fernando *Kitsepawit* Librado indicated that *shiq'o'n* was particularly important on the islands where several families collectively harvested and cooked them in earth ovens measuring more than a meter across. At the Diablo Valdez site, an upland village on the north side of Santa Cruz Island, a well-preserved earth oven dating to ~4500 years ago was identified during excavations. Hundreds of carbonized blue dicks corms were found associated with this feature, confirming its primary function as a means to cook geophytes, and representing the first such feature to be identified archaeologically on the islands. Composite photograph by Kristina Gill, Santa Cruz Island, August 2011.

Several different stages of annual corm morphology are shown here, with modern blue dicks corms on the top row (fibrous coats and basal caps removed), and carbonized archaeobotanical corms identified from the Diablo Valdez site on Santa Cruz Island on the bottom row (not to scale). From left to right, corms exhibit smooth sides (A) in late spring/summer; adventitious roots begin to emerge in early fall, as the corms emerge from summer dormancy (B); adventitious roots continue to grow from around the corm base through the fall months, with scars of fully emerged adventitious roots present on archaeobotanical specimens (C). On archaeobotanical specimens, smooth-sided corms are indicative of a late spring/summer harvest (A), while emerging adventitious roots or root scars are indicative of a fall harvest (B, C). Composite photograph by K. Gill, adapted from Gill 2014.

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